
Artificial Intelligence In Supporting Sustainable Business Model's Development

Dr. Parturkar M. S.

Head & Associate Professor,

Faculty of Commerce, & Management Science,

MSP Mandal's Shri Shivaji College . Basmat Road, Parbhni.

Corresponding Author –Dr. Parturkar M. S.

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.14912780

Abstract:

This research paper aims to shed light on the pivotal role played by artificial intelligence (AI) in supporting sustainable business models' development. It delves into the opportunities AI presents in terms of efficiency, innovation, and problem-solving. However, the paper also acknowledges the critical concerns surrounding AI, including ethical implications, job displacement, and potential biases. By examining the current state of AI research and Business development, the paper proposes a vision policy to guide responsible AI adoption. A comprehensive research methodology is outlined to investigate these opportunities and challenges systematically. The conclusion summarizes the key findings and emphasizes the need for a collaborative approach to AI's benefits while mitigating its risks. With Study entitled "Artificial Intelligence in supporting sustainable business model's development".

Key words: :(AI) Artificial intelligence, (SD) Sustainable Development, (BM)Business Model's.

Introduction:

To achieve this objective, the present study starts by illustrating relevant previous studies about sustainable business models with a specific focus on the economic, social, and environmental (ESG) dimensions of sustainability and by briefly exploring the literature about AI and its potential impacts on business models. Subsequently, the chapter deepens the investigation by developing specific subsections about the implications of adopting AI for each ESG dimension. Each subsection provides an explicative example illustrating how a multinational company (each located in a different country—the United States, Spain, Italy) has implemented AI techniques toward sustainability performance. From automating mundane tasks to making complex decisions, AI has the power to enhance efficiency, drive innovation, and

address pressing global challenges. However, the widespread adoption of AI also raises significant concerns, including ethical considerations, job displacement, and the potential for unintended consequences. This research paper aims to provide a balanced perspective on the opportunities and challenges associated with AI, exploring its potential applications, ethical implications, and the necessary measures to ensure its responsible development.

Objective of the Research paper:

Keeping in view of the significance of the study, the following are the main objectives of the present study.

1. To highlight about AI in supporting sustainable business model's development.

2. To understand the AI in supporting sustainable business model's development.
3. To focus on Importance of AI for sustainable development
4. To study about AI is helping to improve Artificial Intelligence

Hypotheses of the Study:

The following specific hypotheses have been formulated to meet the above objectives of the study.

1. There is big impact of Artificial Intelligence on improve business model's development.
2. There is no big impact of Artificial Intelligence on improve business model's development.

Research Methodology of the Study:

Keeping in view the specific set of objectives enumerated, an in-depth study of Challenges and Opportunities regarding Start-up and Entrepreneurship Development in India.

In this regard methodology needs special emphasis. The Present study is based on collection of data from secondary sources Only.

Sustainability of AI:

The high energy consumption of AI contrasts efficiency gains. The potential of AI technologies can only be fully exploited if costs, effort, and benefits are carefully weighed against the background of the lowest possible consumption of resources. On the one hand, new methods of learning, the reuse of models and more efficient hardware can reduce the required energy. On the other hand, the waste heat from data centers can be used to reduce energy consumption in other areas (e.g. for heating buildings, cooling systems).

Sustainability through AI:

Addressing climate change requires reducing emissions, which necessitates changes in mobility, agriculture, energy, and circular economy, among others, while also requiring adaptation to the impacts of climate change and planning for resilience and disaster management based on an understanding of the climate and extreme events. From startups to mid-sized companies to large corporations, companies are key drivers in the development of AI applications, with many now bringing AI-based solutions to market that help reduce environmental impacts, make systems and processes more resource efficient, and improve systems understanding of the environment and climate. At the same time, there are also many application-oriented research projects at universities to make processes or business models “greener” with the help of AI.

Sustainability with AI:

Artificial Intelligence can also be used to monitor and evaluate the sustainability of companies and to link investment in companies to specific sustainability criteria. There are also promising projects and approaches in nature conservation and environmental monitoring that use AI methods to monitor and evaluate sustainability commitments

Importance of AI for Sustainable Development:

Sustainable development meets the needs of the present without risking that future generations will not be able to meet their own needs. Building on this concept, the global community committed to 17 global goals (UN Sustainable Development Goals) for sustainable development in 2015 under the umbrella of the United Nations with the 2030 Agenda. The guiding principle of the 2030 Agenda is to enable people around the world to live in dignity while

preserving the natural foundations of life in the long term. This includes economic, ecological and social aspects. At the same time, the 2030 Agenda emphasizes the shared responsibility of all actors from politics, business, science, civil society – and every individual. This vision has been translated into Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) that aim to achieve, among other things, a world without poverty and hunger, affordable and clean energy, sustainable consumption and climate protection.

Solutions for more resource-efficient AI technologies:

For the objective evaluation and regulation of AI-related resource consumption, there are several approaches and technological solutions that can already or in the future help to better evaluate, research, and reduce the energy and resource consumption and thus the environmental footprint of deployed AI technologies. These approaches include the following: Sufficiency principle:, Hardware efficiency:, Extending life cycles and circular value chains:, Creating sustainable awareness:, Energy-efficient infrastructure, switching to renewable energy, and intelligent recycling of waste heat:, Reinvestment of saved resources in sustainable processes:, Efficiency instead of expansion – reduction of the absolute energy and resource consumption:, Sustainability by Design:, Federated learning and reuse of model calculations:

Possible design options:

Technological measures, Regulatory approaches, Standardization & interoperability of collected data.

Conclusion of the Study:

The present study pointed out that Numerous application examples already demonstrate that AI has great potential to help us achieve economic, social, and environmental sustainability goals and AI can therefore have a predominantly positive impact on the UN Sustainable Development Goals. The present study Concluded that AI is also expected to impact global productivity, equal opportunity and inclusion, the ecological environment, and several other areas in both the short and long term, if these positive examples can be translated into broad applications and societal acceptance. In this regard, the use of AI can improve people's well-being in many ways, such as by increasing the productivity of services in the areas of food, health, water, education, energy and Business Deployment Model. Lastly study focused on Artificial Intelligence (AI) offers much potential for developing sustainable business models and optimizing existing processes.

Reference:

1. Bassiliades N, Chalkiadakis G (2018) Artificial intelligence techniques for the smart grid. *Adv Build Energy Res* 12(1):1–2
2. Boll, S. & Schnell, M. et al. Working Group Business Modell Innovation, With Artificial Intelligence to sustainable business models.
3. Beltramello A, Haie-Fayle L, Pilat D (2013) Why new business models matter for green growth. OECD Publishing, Paris